

THE POET OF HARMONY AND SEPARATION – FURKAT

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ABSTRACT

An in-depth and comprehensive study of Furkat's life and literary heritage on a scientific basis, as well as all the great representatives of our past literature.

Zokirjon Mullo Kholmukhammad ugli Furkat is one of the leading representatives of Uzbek democratic literature and a poet who made a great contribution to the formation and development of a new enlightenment movement. Furkat is one of the authors who promoted in literature the progressive nature of the new social consciousness born as a result of the annexation of Central Asia to Russia. The poet is an enlightened democratic poet who dedicated his knowledge and all his abilities to the service of the people and sang the song of education, freedom and happiness.

Zokirjon Kholmukhammad ugli Furkat - Uzbek national awakening one of the most prolific representatives of literature. He is a poet and writer, literary critic and he left a rich spiritual legacy as a historian, scholar and translator. Not only this. He was also the first Uzbek journalist in the Turkestan region. There are many literary, political and journalistic articles published in newspapers has not lost its relevance today. Also Furkat was one of the most famous calligraphers of his time. Zokirjon Kholmukhammad o'g'li,

better known by his pen name Furkat, was an Uzbek author, poet, and political activist. He had a major influence on the development of modern Uzbek literature. He wrote one of the earliest pamphlets and satirical articles in Uzbek.

Furkat, like many other writers of the tsarist colonial period, was forced to praise the Russian Empire and its culture in his work. When he started to write poems that were critical of the cruelty of Russian rule, he was exiled to Chinese Turkestan.

He has many disciples in this regard. It is mentioned in the sources that his reputation as a doctor is even higher known to be. He was awarded the title of Zubdatul-Hukamo as proof of his maturity in this regard. He is a tourist in Turkey, in Bulgaria, Greece, Arab countries, as well as India and China it has been. Impressions of the trip, the spiritual world of the people of that time, are different. He wrote down the level of socio-economic development of the states. In short, Furkat, as an encyclopedic scientist and creator, was a person who made a great contribution to the

development of our national spirituality. The study of the poet's works began in his lifetime. Turkistan this is confirmed by the fact that in his thirteenth issue he published a biography of the poet in a provincial newspaper. Significant achievements have been made in the study of the poet's life and work. The bulk of these achievements can be traced back to the Soviet era, and their significance becomes even more apparent when given the study of topics banned by communist ideology. One of the topics covered in Furkat studies during the independence period was Furkat's attitude towards Russian oppression. Research in this area is the work of the poet the uncompromising attitude towards colonial policy, the essence of this policy reveals its purpose and tragic consequences through his works proved that The poet's work in the field of national independence a new aspect that has not been studied at all is religious enlightenment and Sufism is also noteworthy for the publication, promotion and research of his works scientific researches (works of A.Madaminov, N.Jabborov, I.Hakkulov) are carried out. As a result, the religious and mystical themes in Furqat's work are somewhat of the Soviet era transient, as research has shown, "... not typical for him It is scientific that it is one of the main directions, not a reflection of moods based on Like other poets of the Soviet era, he published Furkat's works It was also based on the demands of the communist ideology. Most of it his works have been published in a fragmentary manner with inappropriate abbreviations. There is the results of comparing publications with manuscript sources are their current requirements indicates that it is not at the level of It is only thanks to national independence to think openly, to publish these works in full, to popularize them opportunities arose. As a

result, the poet is still unknown many of his works, their originals, have been identified and researched published. There is no doubt that Furkat was a master of everything he did, whether he was a calligrapher or a writer or a celebrity. According to sources, his calligraphy was very different from the rest, and his handwriting was very ugly. In the field of medicine, according to a number of Furkat scholars, he prevented the mistakes of doctors of his time in medicine. Foreign researchers are also interested in Furkat's personality and literary heritage starting In the East and the West, in the near and far abroad, the life of Furkat and created research on his work. Professor at Columbia University in America E. Allworth, a leading scholar in Turkey, is one of the leaders of the Jadid movement Zaki Validi, Y. Eckman in Hungary, Nematullo in East Turkestan Scholars such as Uбайdullo Haji, Qadir Akbar, Arshildin Totliq describe the life and work of the poet have done remarkable work on research. To national independence in addition to the research mentioned in the period after the achievement of Sh.Yusupov's "Uzbek Enlightenment Literature and Furkat Methodology" manual has been published. N. Jabborov's "Manuscript of Furkat's works sources" was defended. The poet there was a study on participation in the periodical press. Furkat is the first Uzbek theater critic in Sh. Rizaev's "Jadid drama" interpreted as an art critic. This evidence alone is the life of Furkat and The study of creativity took to a whole new level after national independence that there are great opportunities for its further development indicates that Zokirjon Kholmammad his son Furkat with his lyrical poetry It is one of the most important sources of enlightenment in our literature and laid the foundation stone of Uzbek journalism is creative. The poet was born in 1859 in Kokand in a merchant family. His father is a

mullah Kholmuhammad was a poet and an artist. The future poet receives his primary education at a local school. Less than a year Haftiyak and Finishes reading The Four Books. At the age of eight, Fariddin Attor's "Mantiq ut-tayr" memorizes the epic,. From an early age, he practiced poetry with a pencil begins. He later recalled that he had been taught calligraphy since childhood Zakirjon wrote the following verse at the age of nine: "I want to go to school," If it turns out to be my letter, I will spell it. " such verses are an example of his perfect mastery of the field of calligraphy.

"Everyone should be judged by what they do" (Servantes), in this sense, we say: Furkat is the most important part of our national spirituality one of the most iconic figures. His multifaceted creative activity is

undoubtedly important in the development of the nation's youth into well-rounded individuals important. That's why it's important to study his work, to promote his work has a good effect on education. The study of his work is more about the poet helps to create imagination. Furkat is in a time of conflict and danger Although he lived, he left a rich spiritual legacy. His works not only in Uzbek literature, but also abroad. In short, no matter what genre and subject matter fiction is written in, the main goal expected of it is to educate the person. From this point of view, each of the works of Zakirjon Kholmuhammad ugli Furkat has a unique moral, educational and spiritual significance. The general spirit of these works is aimed at educating man in the spirit of perfection.

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